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Executive Summary of White Paper (5000 character limit)

Micro- and nano-satellites offer cost-effective platforms for space technology development and for targeted investigations in astronomy. The original 1999 CubeSat design, based on 1 litre-sized cubes, is now the standard '1U' prototyping architecture. The Canadian Space Agency was an early adopter of micro-satellites. The MOST (Microvariability and Oscillation of Stars) telescope was Canada's first astronomy satellite. Launched in 2003, MOST offered a dedicated platform for asteroseismology that demonstrated the advantages of uninterrupted, long-duration staring observations well before the Kepler Mission adopted the same technique to discover thousands of extrasolar planets. MOST opened the astronomy time domain from space. The subsequent BRITE (BRiGht Target Explorer) Constellation was the first space astronomy mission to be carried out with nano-satellites, with Canada designing all and contributing two of the six 8U-sized satellites. Its greatest advantage was its ability to stay pointed on a wide field (24 x 24 degrees) monitoring up to 30 bright stellar targets for up to 6 months.

Micro-satellite adoption remains slow in astronomy, mostly because of the need for large telescope apertures. However, as demonstrated by MOST and BRITE, time-domain photometry of bright objects, such as Milky Way stars and planetary systems, can be well-served by modest apertures. Improving detector technology is now opening micro-satellite platforms to fainter objects, multi-band photometry, non-optical wavelengths, and polarimetry.

Canada is in a strong position to lead micro-satellite astronomy. Building small and cost-effective - but capable - space platforms will ensure that Canada stays at the forefront of space technology development. Focussing on a few key micro-satellite investigations will optimize the science impact of Canadian space astronomy. Early experience with Canadian micro-satellites also enhances Canadian expertise and HQP training for participation in larger international follow-on missions.

The Canadian Space Agency currently operates two astronomy small-satellite missions, the Near Earth Object Surveillance Satellite (NEOSSat) and BRiGht Target Explorer (BRITE) Constellation, and has two more missions under study: the Photometric Observations of Extrasolar Planets (POEP) and the Extrasolar Planet Polarimetry Explorer / Explorateur Polarimétrique des Planètes Extrasolaires (ÉPPÉ). NEOSSat's first Guest Observer call for proposals in September 2019 was heavily (4.8:1) over-subscribed, reflecting intense astronomy interest. BRITE Constellation has already demonstrated to be one of Canada's highest-publication impact observatories. Both POEP and ÉPPÉ promise novel, science-enabling capabilities in space-based time-domain astronomy with applications well beyond their primary exoplanet-focussed goals. Reliable, dedicated funding to support research with the existing missions and to expand the astronomy small-satellite program will solidify Canada's trademark in space astronomy innovation.

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1 State of Canadian-led Space Astronomy Missions

Canada’s space astronomy portfolio includes Canadian-led micro- or nano-satellite missions and participation in larger international space missions. Micro-sats are spacecraft with mass $\lesssim 100$ kg manufactured from commercial-grade electronic parts by small, experienced teams emphasizing a “build-early, test-often” approach. Nano-sats are smaller still with masses between 1–10 kg. Canada’s micro- and nano-sats have established a track record of successful implementation of commercially developed buses and payloads and high impact for astronomy. We overview the Canadian-led missions, of which there are three (Fig. 1):

- MOST (Microvariability and Oscillations of Stars): 2003–2019;
- NEOSSat (Near-Earth Object Surveillance Satellite): 2013–present;
- BRITE (BRiGht Target Explorer) Constellation: 2013–present.

Figure 1: Renditions of the MOST (left) and NEOSSat (middle) micro-sats in space, and a picture of a BRITE Constellation 8U nano-sat (right) in the lab at UTIAS. Credits: CSA, UTIAS Space Flight Laboratory.

MOST (Walker et al., 2003) was the first astronomy space telescope to implement long uninterrupted staring observations to maximize sensitivity to low-amplitude variability phenomena, including stellar oscillations, rotation, and binarity. Long staring is now the established technique for detecting transiting extrasolar planets, as subsequently implemented by ESA’s CoRoT (Convection, Rotation and planetary Transits; 2006–2014) mission, and that led to the prolific exoplanet yields of NASA’s Kepler (2009–2013), K2 (2013–2018), and Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite (TESS; 2018–present) missions. The same technique has also been used with NASA’s Spitzer (2003–2020) space telescope to study brown dwarf variability and to detect multi-planet transiting extrasolar systems (e.g., Metchev et al., 2015; Gillon et al., 2017).

MOST’s pioneering position meant that it did not have the sensitivity or efficiency of the follow-up missions. MOST had an aperture of 15 cm, a field of view of 0.8° , and a wavelength range of 350–750 nm. However, its effectiveness was demonstrated through key findings in asteroseismology and exoplanets. These include the pioneering use of asteroseismology to determine pre-main sequence evolutionary stages (Zwintz et al., 2014) and the discovery of the first super-Earth exoplanet (55 Cnc e; Winn et al., 2011), among others (Sec. 2.1).

From a technological stand point, MOST established the feasibility of low-cost micro-sat “early-prototyping” architecture with commercial-grade electronics for precise astronomical observations. MOST was made possible through innovative Canadian technology, including very small but robust reaction wheels and magnetometer. The entire life-cycle cost of MOST, including design, construction, launch, and operation was under \$10M. MOST also demonstrated the robustness of Sun-synchronous low-Earth orbits for astronomical observations over more than a decade. The MOST satellite bus and payload architecture served as a basis for NEOSSat.

NEOSSat is a successor to MOST aimed at near-Earth space surveillance. Co-funded by Defence Research & Development Canada (DRDC) and the Canadian Space Agency (CSA), it is the first micro-sat designed to track space debris and other satellites to enhance Space Situational Awareness (SSA). It was also designed to detect near-solar asteroids that are otherwise difficult to observe from the ground. NEOSSat is able to point to within 45° of the Sun thanks to a 90 cm-long baffle, but otherwise shares an optical design similar to MOST.

As the first micro-sat aimed at satellite tracking, NEOSSat experienced operational problems. A post-launch year-2014 evaluation¹ by the CSA indicates that the image quality does not meet the imagery requirements of the scientific aspects of the mission. The detector suffers from variable dark current and electronic interference. Since then, post-processing techniques that account for the deterministic nature of these noise sources have reduced the impact on photometric precision. Recent NEOSSat imagery has demonstrated 1 mmag precision photometry on bright stars with exposure times of a few seconds. An independent year-2016 DRDC evaluation² of the satellite tracking capabilities found that “most NEOSSat observations satisfy the original deep-space SSA science activities devised for the mission in 2009.” However, the report also notes that the calibration of NEOSSat’s metric accuracy is hindered by the low tracking rate of its attitude control system (60 arcsec/sec), which limits the number of detectable GPS calibration satellites at any given time.

As of 2019, NEOSSat is in its extended mission, with the first science Guest Observation (GO1) Program running between September and December 2019. Interest in the GO1 program has been exceptional, with an over-subscription factor of 4.8: in line with the most over-subscribed ground- and space-based international facilities.

BRITE Constellation (Weiss et al., 2014) is a network of six 8U nano-sats designed by the University of Toronto Institute for Aerospace Studies (UTIAS) and launched as a collaboration between Canadian, Polish, and Austrian universities. One of the six nano-sats—one of Canada’s two—did not separate properly from the upper stage of its launch vehicle. Because of the original memorandum of understanding among the three countries, Canadian astronomers can still take full advantage of the mission, despite this loss.

The BRITE satellites are the first nano-sats for astronomy. BRITE follows in the scientific footsteps of MOST in aiming to measure asteroseismic variations to investigate stellar structure and evolution. The wide-field multi-satellite constellation concept is also novel for astronomy, and is used to extend target coverage and to implement dual-band (B and R) observations of many bright targets simultaneously. The 3 cm entrance pupil limits the sensitivity of BRITE to stars brighter than ~ 6 mag.

2 Small-sat Astronomy and Technology Highlights

By offering a dedicated platform for a judiciously chosen experiment, a small-sat can produce an outsized impact on a high-visibility field of science. Small-sats also offer an effective path for developing technologies and methods toward larger future space telescopes.

2.1 Astronomy Highlights

Canadian small-sats have obtained critical observations in exoplanetary science and stellar astrophysics.

- Using MOST detections of the transit of the innermost planet in the 55 Cancri system, Winn et al. (2011) demonstrated that 55 Cnc e was a very short-period (0.74 d) $2R_\oplus$ super-Earth. It was the first super-Earth discovered around a main sequence star. Originally discovered by radial velocity in 2004, prior to its MOST transit detection 55 Cnc e was thought to be a $\geq 14M_\oplus$ giant planet on a 2.8-day orbit (Fischer et al., 2008).
- MOST and CoRoT demonstrated a relationship between the pulsation properties of young stars and their evolutionary state (Zwintz et al., 2014). This was the first application of asteroseismology to pre-main sequence stars. The observations revealed a substantial age spread in the NGC 2264 young open cluster. Zwintz et al. demonstrated that the star formation process in NGC 2264—and likely in other young open

¹<http://www.asc-csa.gc.ca/eng/publications/er-1314-0202.asp>

²http://cradpdf.drdc-rddc.gc.ca/PDFS/unc326/p808033_A1b.pdf

clusters—has been ongoing for much longer than the previously estimated cluster age of 1 to 5 million years.

- MOST offered the unprecedented opportunity to conduct uninterrupted observations on a single astrophysical target for months. When trained for a total of 58 days on the well-known HD 209458b transiting hot Jupiter, MOST revealed it to be extremely dark, with a one-sigma upper limit of 8% on its geometric albedo (Rowe et al., 2008). These measurements presaged future detections of reflected light from transiting extrasolar planets (e.g., CoRoT-1b, Alonso et al. 2009; TrES-2b, Kipping & Spiegel 2011).
- The star β Pictoris hosts the prototype spatially resolved circumstellar debris disk (Smith & Terrile, 1984), and is one of the first stars to have a directly imaged planet (β Pic b; Lagrange et al., 2009, 2010). The planet's 9.7 AU orbit is oriented nearly edge-on, at an inclination of 88.8° (Wang et al., 2016), approximately co-planar with the debris disk. Should there be closer-in planets on co-planar orbits, they may transit in front of the host star. BRITE Constellation was the perfect platform to test for their existence. A 78-day continuous campaign with BRITE excluded any <30 day planets co-planar with β Pic b (Mol Lous et al., 2018).
- The BRITE Constellation collaboration has produced 46 refereed publications with 238 unique refereed citations since the launch of the first BRITE nano-sats in 2013.³ Having been published only in the past six years, most of these papers have yet to reach their full impact. Nevertheless, at an average citation rate of 5.2 per paper, BRITE Constellation already outpaces all major ground-based facilities (cf. Fig. 2-12 in the CASCA 2010 Long-Range Plan “Unveiling the Cosmos”).⁴ With a total cost of $< \$12$ M, BRITE Constellation may well offer among the highest return on investment in terms of scientific impact compared to any ground- or space-based telescope.
- In an example of high-impact ancillary science from a non-astronomy satellite, Macdonald & Cowan (2019) adopt data from the Canadian SCISAT Earth observation small-sat to measure the 2–14 μ m infrared transit spectrum of Earth. To this end, they co-add 14 years of SCISAT observations through Earth's atmosphere toward the Sun. The measurement sets the ground truth for future atmospheric characterization of transiting extrasolar Earth analogues with the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST).

2.2 Technology Highlights

Canada now boasts several organizations, including Microsat Systems Canada Inc. (MSCI), Honeywell Aerospace Co. (formerly COM DEV Intl.), Magellan Aerospace Co., and the UTIAS Space Flight Laboratory (SFL), that all have demonstrated capabilities in small-sat manufacturing. This is a strategic national capability, as the international exchange of space technology is limited by export control considerations.

- The multi-mission micro-sat bus developed by MSCI, initially for MOST and then for several subsequent micro-sat missions including NEOSat, has generated significant commercial interest internationally. MSCI has announced intention to build an 84 satellite system in low-Earth orbit, consisting of 78 satellites in six polar orbital planes with a spare in each orbit.⁵ The MSCI multi-mission micro-sat bus is also a potential carrier for future CSA (e.g., POEP; Sec. 4.1) or Department of National Defence missions.
- The three satellite buses for CSA's most recent Earth observation mission, RADARSAT Constellation Mission, were built by Magellan Aerospace. Magellan was also the prime contractor for SCISAT, launched in 2003 on a two-year mission but still operational today, and provided their MAC-200 multi-mission small satellite bus for the telecommunications/ionospheric research satellite CASSIOPE (CAScade, Smallsat and IONospheric Polar Explorer), launched in 2013. Magellan's new MAC-300 micro-sat bus concept is at the design basis for the proposed ÉPPÉ mission (Sec. 4.2).

³Source: NASA ADS. Search parameters (year:2013-2019 +abs:“brite”), selecting unique, refereed, astronomy-only collections.

⁴https://www.casca.ca/lrp2010/11093_AstronomyLRP_V16web.pdf

⁵“Evaluation of the Near Earth Object Surveillance Satellite (NEOSat) Project” report by the Audit and Evaluation Directorate of the CSA; <http://www.asc-csa.gc.ca/eng/publications/er-1314-0202.asp>

- The Canadian Advanced Nanospace eXperiment (CanX) program at UTIAS SFL provides cost-effective access to space through the use of nano-sats. BRITE Constellation is the third iteration (CanX-3) of the program and the first set of astronomy nano-sats. The CanX program has also successfully demonstrated cost-effective formation flying (CanX-4 and CanX-5), and tracking of ocean ships (CanX-6) and airplanes (CanX-7).

3 Canadian Micro-sats and Other 2020–2030 Space Missions: Context and Opportunities

Current micro-sat buses limit the diameter of the primary optical element to about 15 cm, as in MOST and NEOSat. Efficient optical monitoring with such capacity is already being performed with TESS, which combines four 10 cm apertures that each feed a $24^\circ \times 24^\circ$ visible-light ($0.6\text{--}1.0\ \mu\text{m}$) camera. The TESS lenses have a combined field of view of $24^\circ \times 96^\circ$ ($2,300\ \text{deg}^2$, around 5% of the entire sky) and a focal ratio of $f/1.4$. While TESS's original mission was 2 years (2018–2020), it has been extended through at least 2022. Because of its stable 2:1 lunar resonance orbit, TESS can in principle operate for decades.

The pending (late 2019) launch of ESA's CHEOPS (CHaracterising ExOPlanet Satellite) will add a dedicated capability for visible-light photometric monitoring of exoplanets with a larger, 30 cm aperture. Continuing operation of the Hubble Space Telescope ($0.17\text{--}1.80\ \mu\text{m}$ photometry and spectroscopy), and in the future also JWST (2021+; $0.6\text{--}27\ \mu\text{m}$ photometry and spectroscopy), WFIRST ($\sim 2025+$; $0.48\text{--}2.00\ \mu\text{m}$ photometry and spectroscopy), PLATO (2026+; $0.5\text{--}1.0\ \mu\text{m}$ photometry), ARIEL (2028+; $0.5\text{--}7.8\ \mu\text{m}$ spectroscopy), and potentially CASTOR (2027+; $0.15\text{--}0.55\ \mu\text{m}$ photometry and spectroscopy) will round out UV/optical/IR space-based telescopes into the end of the 2021–2030 decade.

In the context of large, heavily over-subscribed space astronomy facilities, micro-sats will continue to offer unique advantages and complementarity with dedicated observing time, measurement stability, and uninterrupted monitoring cadence. With capabilities in visible-light micro-sat photometry now well-established, and with small apertures largely precluding relevant spectroscopically dispersed observations, the next niche for micro-sats is at non-optical (e.g., UV, IR) wavelengths or in polarimetric observations. Not only will such capacities open the multi-wavelength time domain to precision photometry; they will also augment the impact of other major facilities (HST, JWST, PLATO, ARIEL, CASTOR) with contemporaneous observations at complementary wavelengths or in polarized light.

4 New Astronomy Small-sat Mission Studies at the CSA

In 2018 the CSA issued requests for proposals for Science Maturation Studies (SMS) and Concept Studies (CS) in the science priorities of Planetary Exploration and Space Astronomy. These priorities were set in the Community

Figure 2: Detection of Rayleigh scattering in exoplanetary atmospheres with differential u - and i -band photometry on POEP. An HST transmission spectrum of HD 189733b (black data points; Sing et al., 2011) is compared to a combined Rayleigh scattering ($1340 \pm 150\ \text{K}$; red solid and dashed lines) and haze-free atmospheric model from Fortney et al. (2010). The ≈ 1000 ppm difference between the u - and i -band transit depths measures the Rayleigh slope and will be easily discernible at the 10–100 ppm photometric precision of POEP. (Based on Figure 14 from Sing et al. 2011).

Report⁶ from the 2016 Canadian Space Exploration Workshop (CSEW) and Topical Teams. The recommendations on Space Astronomy in the CSEW Community Report were themselves informed by the prior 2010 CASCA Long Range Plan and 2015 Mid-Term Review.

Two small-sat astronomy mission concepts were selected for study in Space Astronomy: an SMS on “Photometric Observations of Extrasolar Planets” (POEP) and a CS for the “Extrasolar Planet Polarimetry Explorer” (ÉPPÉ). The remaining SMS and CS Space Astronomy selections funded on-going work on CASTOR, the JAXA-led LiteBIRD microwave telescope, and the proposed Colibrì x-ray telescope.⁷

Both small-sat concepts, POEP and ÉPPÉ build on space-proven bus heritage. They would offer new science capabilities that complement larger missions, and would have broad relevance beyond their focus on extra-solar planets.

4.1 Photometric Observations of Extrasolar Planets (POEP)

This provisionally named mission has the dual science objectives of characterizing known transiting extrasolar planets and of discovering new ones. The exoplanet characterization goal will be achieved through dual *u*- and *i*-band transit photometry (Fig. 2) to measure the extent of hot-Jupiter atmospheres through Rayleigh scattering. These determinations will improve knowledge of exoplanet fundamental parameters and will establish a legacy for long-term precision timing of transit events, e.g., for further spectroscopic characterization with JWST, ARIEL, or CASTOR. The exoplanet discovery goal will use precision *i*-band photometry to detect small, potentially rocky and habitable transiting exoplanets around ultra-cool (>M7) dwarfs, has been added to the stellar light curve. Single transits of Earth-sized rocky exoplanets are detectable around host stars down to $I \approx 13$ mag or $J \approx 13$ mag. However, there are over twice as many $J < 13$ mag than $I < 13$ mag ultra-cool dwarfs.

These faintest of low-mass stars and brown dwarfs remain beyond the photometric grasp of TESS. Yet, because of favourable planet-to-star flux ratios, any planets orbiting around ultra-cool dwarfs would offer some of the best opportunities for atmospheric characterization and biosignature detection: with JWST or with ground-based extremely large telescopes. Beyond the field of exoplanets, the dual-band capability of POEP will also allow studies of hot white dwarfs in close/interacting binaries, the flaring properties of M dwarfs, and stellar pulsations, interiors and evolution.

The baseline POEP mission is a 15-cm space telescope on the well-tested MSCI multi-mission satellite bus with legacy from MOST and NEOSat. The telescope would feed dual-CCD (*u*- and *i*-band) detectors to create an efficient photometer. The detectors would be used interchangeably for science or guidance imaging. The spacecraft would be placed in an 800 km Sun-synchronous orbit. The payload would have a continuous viewing zone between approximately -20° and $+30^\circ$ in declination, and will be capable of staring at a single field for up to two months. A launch is possible as soon as 2025, with a minimum mission lifetime of two years.

Figure 3: Simulated POEP transit observations of a $1R_{\oplus}$ planet around a main-sequence $0.08M_{\odot}$ star ($I - J = 2.0$ mag). The *y* axis shows normalized flux (NF) for host star brightness in the $12 < I < 16$ mag (left panel) or $10 < J < 14$ mag (right panel) range. A 0.5% semi-amplitude 3 h period rotational modulation, typical of spotted ultra-cool (>M7) dwarfs, has been added to the stellar light curve. Single transits of Earth-sized rocky exoplanets are detectable around host stars down to $I \approx 13$ mag or $J \approx 13$ mag. However, there are over twice as many $J < 13$ mag than $I < 13$ mag ultra-cool dwarfs.

⁶“Canadian Space Exploration: Science and Space Health Priorities for Next Decade and Beyond”; <http://www.exoplanetes.umontreal.ca/wp-content/uploads/2018/10/Canadian-Space-Exploration-Science-and-Space-Health-priorities-for-Next-Decade-and-Beyond-2017.pdf>

⁷Cassiopeia Newsletter – Autumnal Equinox / Equinoxe d’automne 2019; <https://casca.ca/?p=12617>

Options for an augmented POEP mission are also considered: e.g., substituting one or both of the u - and i -band detectors with a near-UV and/or near-IR J -band detectors. These could offer a broader baseline for atmospheric characterization, greater sensitivity to Rayleigh scattering, a factor of >2 larger sample of ultra-cool dwarfs for rocky planet transit searches (Fig. 3; right), and greater diagnostic power for hot white dwarf, M dwarf, and astero-seismology studies. Dedicated near-UV/near-IR monitoring from space will be entirely novel and science-enabling.

4.2 Extrasolar Planet Polarimetry Explorer / Explorateur Polarimétrique des Planètes Extrasolaires (ÉPPÉ)

The ÉPPÉ small-sat concept would be the first dedicated space-based precision optical polarimeter. Ancillary polarimetric capability existed in space on the HST NICMOS and ACS cameras, where it produced $\approx 1\%$ – 5% -precision polarimetric measurements of, e.g., dust-scattered light in circumstellar disks (Graham et al., 2007; Perrin et al., 2009). The only other dedicated space-based polarimeter was the Wisconsin Ultraviolet Photo-Polarimeter Experiment (WUPPE; Bjorkman et al., 1991) flown on two Space Shuttle missions in the pre-exoplanet era (December 2–11, 1990 and March 2–18, 1995). Among other results, WUPPE obtained the first UV spectro-polarimetric measurements of sunlight reflected by solar-system bodies (Fox et al., 1997, 1998).

Differential polarimetry is a powerful technique that can detect and characterize planetary surfaces and atmospheres (Fig. 4). It can reveal the net polarization signature of exoplanets if the integrated emission from the host star is—as expected—unpolarized. In contrast to current follow-up methods, polarimetry is equally well-suited to studying non-transiting exoplanets, preferentially around brighter stars. A space-based differential polarimetry platform will also be able to characterize massive-star circumstellar environments and stellar-wind bow shocks (Shrestha et al., 2018), surface convection of evolved stars (López Ariste et al., 2018), and radial pulsations that create asymmetries in the stellar shape and thus probe stellar interiors (López Ariste et al., 2019). Long, uninterrupted polarisation observations of stars have never been done and are certain to generate new results.

State-of-the-art ground-based differential polarimetry with the POLISH2 instrument on a non-optimized telescope has reached a sensitivity of 10 ppm (Wiktorowicz et al., 2015). POLISH2 features a photo-electric modulator crystal that rapidly switches the polarization vector. Both polarization states follow the same optical path and are read out in quick succession by a photomultiplier tube (Wiktorowicz & Nofi, 2015). ÉPPÉ would be designed similarly, and will further benefit from a bus and payload that are optimized for precision polarimetry. ÉPPÉ aims to achieve a photon noise floor of <1 ppm in broad-band (350–850 nm) visible light from space.

ÉPPÉ is envisaged as a 30 cm telescope housed in a bus that is nominally 60 cm to a side: i.e., somewhat larger than a micro-sat. ÉPPÉ would use Magellan’s new MAC-300 satellite bus design, with heritage from the MAC-200 bus used for CASSIOPE. A Sun-synchronous low-Earth orbit will enable on-target stares for up to two months. ÉPPÉ is expected to detect reflected light from super-Earths as small as $1.5R_{\oplus}$ over a three-year mission life time.

Figure 4: Ground-based 550 nm measurements of the polarization of Venus as a function of scattering phase angle and cloud particle size (Hansen & Hovenier, 1974). Zero and 180° phases produce zero polarization. The greatest degree of polarization is seen most consistently near normal-angle scattering. The phase dependence of the polarization can reveal the sizes and compositions of atmospheric cloud particles. Similar observable polarization behaviour is expected to be detectable by ÉPPÉ from the atmospheres of known $>1.5R_{\oplus}$ exoplanets.

5 Recommendations

Small-sats have a track record of delivering low-cost high-impact science and rapid space technology advancement that complement larger missions. Canada's space industry has a mature and proven capacity to produce small-sats: the result of targeted government investment in space technology over the past two decades. This offers an exciting opportunity to expand small-sat astronomy into new wavelength regimes (*u*-band/near-UV/near-IR) and operation modes (dual-band imaging, polarimetry), where even small dedicated platforms can produce ground-breaking science.

The suite of Canadian-led space astronomy missions (MOST, BRITE Constellation, NEOSSat) has already had an outsized impact. However, with the last launches (BRITE and NEOSSat) dating back to 2013, and with other small-sat launches in the planning internationally, Canada's astronomy small-sat program needs new impetus to maintain competitive advantage. Further investment in small-sat telescopes can open new trademark areas for Canadian space astronomy, and will so strengthen Canadian leadership in the space sector. We recommend:

- A Phase 0 study for the POEP mission. POEP will be a dedicated, diagnostic dual-band micro-sat photometer. Its primary science is well-aligned with top priorities in Canadian astronomy: the characterization of exoplanetary atmospheres and the detection of rocky, potentially habitable exoplanets. POEP will complement unfiltered visible-light photometry from NASA's TESS, ESA's upcoming CHEOPS mission (late-2019 launch), and will aid science with future facility UV/optical/IR space telescopes (JWST, WFIRST, PLATO, ARIEL, CASTOR).
- Further development of the ÉPPÉ mission concept. As the first space-based precision polarimeter, ÉPPÉ has significant science-enabling potential that is well-aligned with top priorities in Canadian astronomy and goes much beyond the characterization of exoplanetary atmospheres. ÉPPÉ could address questions in solar system astronomy, magnetically active stars, stellar structure, circumstellar environments, the interstellar medium, and any other source of astrophysical polarization. An SMS and separate payload funding from CSA's Space Technology Development Program can advance ÉPPÉ to Phase 0 readiness level.
- Continued NEOSSat operations along with funding for the newly established GO program. NEOSSat complements TESS capabilities in being able to follow-up discoveries beyond the 27.4 day TESS observing window. NEOSSat's Sun-synchronous low-Earth orbit allows prolonged stares that could further provide critical monitoring for host-star variability simultaneously with longer-wavelength JWST exoplanet spectroscopy after 2021. The factor of 4.8 over-subscription of the NEOSSat GO1 cycle shows resounding interest from Canadian astronomers.
- An increased, dedicated micro-sat budget in the CSA portfolio for rapid development, testing, and more regular satellite launches. These should include opportunities for both low-Earth and higher orbits that could offer better thermal stability for the satellites. Of interest in particular are stable near-lunar TESS-like orbits that could be reached as part of multi-payload missions to the future Lunar Gateway.

1: How does the proposed initiative result in fundamental or transformational advances in our understanding of the Universe?

Dedicated space-based astronomy platforms can be used to solve specific questions of broad significance. MOST opened the astronomy time-domain from space, and demonstrated the milli-magnitude precision needed for detecting rocky exoplanets. Specialized small-sat telescopes can similarly address fundamental questions through dedicated observations. Micro-sats present an effective and low-cost platform for rapid technology and methodology innovation that complements larger flagship missions in our pursuit to understand the Universe.

2: What are the main scientific risks and how will they be mitigated?

The main scientific risks are in implementing new technologies on small-sat platforms. However, there is substantial heritage from previous and current small-sats in visible-wavelength imaging. Technology development can be furthered through suborbital or cube-sat tests as part of a regular CSA-funded opportunity cycle.

3: Is there the expectation of and capacity for Canadian scientific, technical or strategic leadership?

Canada has strong heritage in developing small-sats for remote sensing with applications to both astronomy and Earth observations. Examples include MOST, CASSIOPE, BRITE, NEOSSat, and SCISAT, built through partnerships among various members of the Canadian space sector (MDA, ABB, Magellan Aerospace, UTIAS SFL, and others). Canada has the capacity to lead innovation in small-sat astronomy. Small-sat missions also present an excellent opportunity to train and sustain a robust, experienced workforce within the space sector, that can lead larger Canadian flagship space missions in the future.

4: Is there support from, involvement from, and coordination within the relevant Canadian community and more broadly?

The principal science cases for small-sats are focused on solar system, exoplanetary, and stellar astronomy. There is both strong heritage and continued coordination within the relevant communities to continue these developments. Many of the representative members of the community are co-signers of this white paper. Separately, the CSA has recently funded studies toward future Canadian small-sats.

5: Will this program position Canadian astronomy for future opportunities and returns in 2020–2030 or beyond 2030?

Small-sats have a relatively short development cycle: between 6–9 years from Phase 0 to launch. Investment in small-sats will offer prompt scientific pay-offs before the end of the 2020's decade and an opportunity to quickly advance and space-test technologies for larger space telescopes in the 2030's. The highly-qualified workforce that will be trained in the process will constitute a strategic intellectual resource that will be well-positioned to take on leadership roles in these larger future missions.

6: In what ways is the cost-benefit ratio, including existing investments and future operating costs, favourable?

Small-sats have life-cycle costs that are a fraction of the cost of a flagship mission. MOST's life-cycle cost over nearly 16 years in operations was <\$10M, whereas the BRITE mission cost is <\$12M. The science impact from BRITE (and likely from MOST) clearly compares favourably to large ground-based facilities (Sec. 2.1). Ultimately, both small- and large-scale investments are needed to advance Canadian astronomy. The advantage of small-sat technology is that it can be more readily Canadian-led. It demonstrates Canadian leadership in the high-visibility space sector and furthers domestic space capabilities.

7: What are the main programmatic risks and how will they be mitigated?

The main programmatic risk is inadequate funding. Funding for mission studies and mission construction is awarded either directly from the CSA or through a co-funding model that requires inter-department government agreements or international partnerships. However, operating costs for extending missions beyond

baseline can be problematic. The only avenue to support mission operations is the CSA, and presently that resource is insufficient. Recommendations for increased CSA research funding are detailed in LRP2020 white paper E005 (“Space Astronomy”; J. Hutchings).

Additional risks lie in the integration of the mixed academic, industrial, and government partnerships. Unlike NASA’s federally-funded space laboratories, astronomy research and space engineering in Canada are conducted largely without in-kind involvement from CSA personnel. NEOSSat’s below-spec science performance is an example of this integration not proceeding smoothly. The CSA has now taken over the mission from the primary contractor. With a larger dedicated human resource, NEOSSat has resumed science operations and is entering an extended mission. Risk mitigation therefore relies on regular contact among the academic and industrial partners and the CSA, on availability of well-trained personnel, and critically: on funding.

8: Does the proposed initiative offer specific tangible benefits to Canadians, including but not limited to interdisciplinary research, industry opportunities, HQP training, EDI, outreach or education?

As a result of government investment in small-sat technology, Canada’s space industry has developed world-leading capabilities for both scientific and commercial applications. Continued support for the space sector is creating an attractive and inclusive labour market for HQP within Canada. The associated domestic expertise in space science, engineering, and mission management is essential training for the leaders of future space missions: as illustrated by the current interested parties, many of whom were young participants in MOST and BRITE. Space astronomy is also highly visible in the public eye, and offers excellent opportunities for education and outreach.

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